

THE
SALTICIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA
K-Magnus

Compiled by: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, C.R. Haddad, V. van der Walt, S.H. Foord†, L.N. Lotz & W. Uys

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Menemerus bifurcus ©Vida van der Walt

THE SALTICIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA PART 4 (*K–Mogrus*)

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The family Salticidae is the largest spider family known from 689 genera and 6809 species. From South Africa, 85 genera and 363 species are known (World Spider Catalog, 2026). The Salticidae Guides are arranged into seven volumes:

Part 1: *Aelurillus* to *Dendryphantas* 41 species (63 pp.)

Part 2: *Euophrys* to *Hasarius* 49 species (65 pp.)

Part 3: *Heliophanus* to *Iranattus* 74 species (75 pp.)

Part 4: *Kima* to *Mogrus* 51 species (67 pp.) ←

Part 5: *Myrmarachne* to *Pignus* 53 species (66 pp.)

Part 6: *Planamarengo* to *Tanzania* 55 species (60 pp.)

Part 7: *Tenuiballus* to *Zulunigma* 58 species (66 pp.).

In Part 4, the maps were compiled by Dr. Wynand Uys and include distribution data from the SANSA database as well as research grade locations downloaded from iNaturalist. In the text, the iNaturalist records are marked with an asterisk.

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GENUS *KIMA* Peckham & Peckham, 1902

The genus *Kima* Peckham & Peckham, 1902 is known from five African species, with three species known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Kima Jumping Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Kima africana* Peckham & Peckham, 1902

MORPHOLOGY: Slender spiders with long legs, total length 8–10 mm. Carapace dark, with translucent or scattered white setae; carapace long, with sides almost parallel; with transverse constriction behind posterior eye row; thoracic part distinctly lower than cephalic region; anterior eyes placed close together, forming row that is slightly curved downward; middle eyes about twice as large as laterals. Abdomen with distinct pedicel; elongated, with constriction near middle of abdomen; dark and decorated with transverse black stripes or spots or whole abdomen covered with scale-like setae. Legs long and slender; leg formula 4132, fourth clearly longest; legs dark, frequently decorated with paler longitudinal bands. Female slightly larger than male but abdomen not as slender, patterns similar to those of male.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dwellers frequently associated with ants. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes.

TAXONOMY: Two of the species known from South Africa were described by Peckham & Peckham (1902). They were included in a revision by Wesołowska & Szeremeta (2001).

Figs 1–3. *Kima* spp. 1. *Kima* sp. 2. *Kima africana*. 3. Line drawing of male habitus, lateral view. Credits: 1. Vida van der Walt. 2. Alan Manson. 3. From Wesołowska & Szeremeta (2001).

Kima africana Peckham & Peckham, 1902

COMMON NAME: Yellow Kima Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1902, with the type locality only given as Cape Colony. The species is presently known from three provinces (EOO=158 793 km²; AOO=40 km²; 7–1531 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.17, 26.50). **Northern Cape:** Calvinia, Downes Farm (-31.50, 19.96)*; Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Zeekoegat (-30.61, 22.446)*. **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Malmesbury (-33.76, 18.23)*; Montagu (-33.76, 20.12)*; Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Strandfontein (-31.76, 18.23)*. * from iNaturalist

LIFESTYLE: *Kima africana* is a rare free-living ground-dweller found running around during the day. They have been recorded in the more arid regions, where they mimic *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ants as a survival strategy (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2025). Their myrmecomorphic morphology helps them avoid predators that typically steer clear of ants due to their aggressive behavior and chemical defenses. Their body shape, with the long pedicel and yellow setae on the abdomen, resembles the model ant (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2025). They have been found in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Nama Karoo, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes. In the Northern Cape, were sampled on the edge of pistachio orchards.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the female. Presently protected in the Tsolwana Nature Reserve and Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2023).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Peckham & Peckham, 1902). It was redescribed by Wesołowska and Szeremeta (2001). The abdomen, which has a constriction in the middle, is covered with yellow to golden, scale-like setae dorsally.

Figs 1–7. *Kima africana* male. 1–3. Male from Calvinia. 4, 5. Male palp. 6. Palpal femur. 7. Cheliceral dentition. Credits: 1–3. Alan Manson. 4. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. 5–7. From Wesołowska & Szeremeta (2001).

Kima variabilis Peckham & Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Kima Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1903 from Cape Town in the Western Cape. Sampled in South Africa from five provinces (EOO=539 521 km²; AOO=32 km²; 7–895 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Great Fish River Reserve (-33.13, 26.65); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Phinda Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.27). **Limpopo:** Karongwe Game Reserve (-24.20, 30.54)*; Makuleke Concession, Kruger National Park (-22.357, 31.171)*. **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Malmesbury (-33.47, 18.74)*; Tierberg, Prince Albert (-33.13, 22.25).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the female. Protected in the Great Fish River Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve and Phinda Game Reserve, as well as the Tierberg Long Term Ecological Research site, Prince Albert (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Peckham & Peckham, 1903). Revised by Wesołowska & Szeremeta (2001). Although the female has been collected, it remains undescribed.

Figs 1–8. *Kima variabilis*. 1. Male. 2–4. Undescribed female from Irene. 5. Male palp. 6. Cheliceral dentition. 7. Palpal femur. 8. Male habitus. Credits. 1. A. Martin. 2–4. Vida van der Walt. 5–7. From Wesołowska & Szeremeta (2001). 8. From Peckham & Peckham (1903).

GENUS *LANGELURILLUS* Próchniewicz, 1994

The genus *Langelurillus* Próchniewicz, 1994 is known from 23 species (World Spider Catalog, 2025), with 20 species recorded from Africa and three from India.

COMMON NAME: Langelurillus jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Langelurillus primus* Próchniewicz, 1994

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace high and distinctly convex, longer than broad, widest at level of coxae III. Sides truncate, anterior eye row recurved. Eye field short, distinctly darker than thorax; cephalic region rectangular, broader than long, eyes forming square; thorax with single light median band and paler sides, covered with scale-like hairs; clypeus narrower than or equal to diameter of anterior median eyes; cheliceral margins toothless. Abdomen ovoid, males of some species with rectangular dorsal scutum. Legs III longest.

LIFESTYLE: Some specimens were collected in leaf litter, where they were found foraging on *Odontotermes* termites (Haddad, pers. obs.).

TAXONOMY: Seven species are known from South Africa and have been reported on by Haddad & Wesolowska (2013), Wesolowska & Cumming (2011), Wesolowska & Haddad (2013) and Wesolowska (2011).

Figs 1–2. *Langelurillus squamiger* female from Tembe Elephant Park. Credit: Ruan Booysen.

Figs 3–4. *Langelurillus* sp. female from Malmesbury. Credit: Cecile Roux.

Langelurillus cedarbergensis Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013

COMMON NAME: Cederberg Langelurillus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic species described in 2013 from the Cederberg Mountains (EOO=<math><100\text{ km}^2</math>; AOO=4 km²; 964 m a.s.l.). The species is only known from females collected at the type locality, and its status remains obscure as the male remains unknown. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Cederberg Mountains, 17 km SE of Algeria (-32.42, 19.17).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling spider sampled with pitfall traps from the drier parts of the Fynbos Biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION STATUS: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only the female is known (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013). This species is similar to *Langelurillus namibicus* Wesolowska, 2011, but can be distinguished by the structure of the epigyne.

Figs 1–4. *Langelurillus cedarbergensis* female. 1. Habitus. 2. Carapace. 3–4. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2, 4. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2013). 3. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Langelurillus krugeri Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Kruger Park Langelurillus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described in 2013 from the Kruger National Park (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 304 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure as the male has never been discovered. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Kruger National Park, Mopani, Tsendze (-23.69, 31.52).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling spider collected from woodland in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION STATUS: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013). Carapace high, with very steep posterior thoracic slope, pear-shaped, widest at coxae III. Colouration of carapace blackish, dorsum covered with diminutive hairs adpressed to surface, with numerous long brown bristles on anterior part of eye field. Clypeus moderately high, dark, with long dark bristles. Abdomen large, rounded, slightly swollen, brownish grey with ill-defined lighter patches; clothed in brown hairs, with scattered long brown bristles, denser anteriorly. Venter dark.

Fig. 1. *Langelurillus krugeri* epigyne. From Wesolowska & Haddad (2013).

Langelurillus minutus Wesolowska & Cumming, 2011

COMMON NAME: Small Langelurillus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described in 2011 from Zimbabwe. The species has been recorded from four southern African countries. In South Africa, it has only been sampled from the Limpopo Province (EOO=17 307 km²; AOO=20 km²; 575–905 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.41, 26.75); Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.14, 29.92); Limpopo Valley, Farm Stoke (-22.48, 29.88); Vhembe Biosphere, Farm Ludwig's Lust (-22.24, 29.78).

LIFESTYLE: Litter-dweller sampled with pitfall traps in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION STATUS: No known threats. In South Africa, sampled from two protected areas: Ben Lavin Nature Reserve and Atherstone Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska & Cumming, 2011).

Figs 1–7. *Langelurillus minutus*. 1. Male habitus. 2. Female habitus. 3. Abdomen. 4–5. Epigyne. 6, 7. Palp. From Haddad *et al.* (2025).

Langelurillus namibicus Wesolowska, 2011

COMMON NAME: Namibian Langelurillus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2011 from Namibia. Also recorded from South Africa (EOO=<1000 km²; AOO=12 km²; 759–1155 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical African range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Kruger National Park (-23.65, 31.57). *Northern Cape*: Kamiesberg mountains, 23 km E of Kamieskroon (-30.20, 17.93); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling spider sampled from the Succulent Karoo and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION STATUS: It is presently protected in the Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2019) and Kruger National Park. More sampling is needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from the female (Wesolowska, 2011).

Fig. 1. *Langelurillus namibicus* epigyne. From Wesolowska (2011).

Langelurillus squamiger Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018

COMMON NAME: Tembe Langelurillus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic species described in 2018 from Tembe Elephant Park (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 88 m a.s.l.). Only known from the type locality. More sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Tembe Elephant Park (-26.98, 32.47).

LIFESTYLE: This species was collected in leaf litter in Maputaland sand forests, where it was found foraging together with two termitophagous jumping spider species, *Stenaelurillus guttiger* Simon, 1901 and *S. modestus* Wesolowska, 2014, as well as *Habrocestum africanum* Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009.

CONSERVATION STATUS: There are no known threats, although it occurs in a threatened, range-restricted forest type (sand forest). It is protected in the Tembe Elephant Park. More sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018).

Figs 1–8. *Langelurillus squamiger*. 1–2. Male habitus. 3–5. Female habitus. 6. Epigyne. 7, 8. Male palp. Credits: 1–3, 6–8. From Wesolowska & Haddad (2018). 4, 5. Ruan Booysen.

GENUS *LANGONA* Simon, 1901

The genus *Langona* Simon, 1901 is known from 46 species (World Spider Catalog, 2026) with 28 species known from Africa.

COMMON NAME: Langona Jumping Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Attus redii* Audouin, 1826.

MORPHOLOGY: Morphologically, all *Langona* species are very similar, dark coloured with a characteristic lighter striped pattern. The males have a single tibial apophysis, usually accompanied by a tuft of long black setae, and the embolus coiled on the tip of the tegulum. The females have an epigyne with a large central depression, the posterior edge of which is very strongly sclerotized. The internal structure of the epigyne is very complicated, with multi-chambered receptacles.

LIFESTYLE: They are litter-dwellers and have been frequently sampled from pitfall traps, particularly in arid and semi-arid areas.

TAXONOMY: Seven species have been recorded from South Africa.

Figs 1–4. *Langona* spp. females. 1, 2. *Langona hirsuta* from Otto's Den. 3, 4. *Langona bisecta* from Gundani. Credits: 1, 2. Wynand Uys. 3, 4. Peter Webb.

Langona bethae Wesolowska & Cumming, 2011

COMMON NAME: Beth's Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described in 2011 from Zimbabwe. It has been recorded from three southern African countries. In South Africa, it has been sampled from the Northern Cape and Limpopo provinces (EEO=<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 955–1212 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Vhuvha Communal land (-22.99, 30.18); Vhuvha Communal land (-22.91, 30.03). **Northern Cape:** Meerkat National Park (-30.77, 21.25)*; Sendelingsdrift (-28.18, 17.04)*.

LIFESTYLE: Litter-dweller sampled from the pitfall traps in the Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. The species receives some protection in the Meerkat National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska & Cumming, 2011), with Wesolowska (2011) adding additional records.

Figs 1–7. *Langona bethae*. 1, 2. Female and male in alcohol material. 3, 4. Female from Sendelingsdrif. 5. Abdomen. 6. Epigyne. 7. Male palp. Credits: 1, 2, 5–7. From Wesolowska & Cumming (2011). 3, 4. Ruan Booysen.

Langona bisecta Lawrence, 1927

COMMON NAME: Namibian Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1927 from Namibia. Also recorded from South Africa from the Limpopo Province (EEO=1491 km²; AOO=12 km²; 78–1025 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.36, 29.31); Gundani Forest (-22.65, 30.53); Soutpansberg Conservancy (-23.21, 29.51).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dwellers, sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. The species receives some protection in the Soutpansberg Conservancy.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from the female (Lawrence, 1927).

Figs 1–6. *Langona bisecta* female. 1–4. Female from Gundani. 5, 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1–4. Peter Webb. 5. From Lawrence (1927). 6. Ansie Dippenaar–Schoeman.

Langona hirsuta Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011

COMMON NAME: Hairy Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2011 from Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve in the Free State. Sampled from five South African provinces, including >10 protected areas (EOO=426 282 km²; AOO=156 km²; 14–1768 m a.s.l.). Due to its broad distribution, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free State: Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein district, Krugersdrift Dam (-28.70, 25.92); Boshof district, Farm Kromrant (-28.65, 25.10); Bothaville district, Farm Deelfontein (-27.12, 26.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Jacobsdal district, Jacobsdal-Kimberley road (-29.18, 24.77); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.59, 25.45).

Limpopo: Leggalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17 30.25); Otters Den Island, Blyde River (-24.41, 30.81)*; Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Springbokvlakte, Tweekansen (-25.48, 28.56); Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.32). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.30, 24.81); Kimberley district, Farm Langberg (-28.92, 24.60); Oryx Game Farm (-28.41, 22.17); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.67, 24.30); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Cederberg, Aan Het Berg (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg, Driehoek, 930 m a.s.l. (-32.42, 19.16); Cederberg, Niewoudt's Pass, 527 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg, Niewoudt's Pass, 565 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 19.00); Cederberg, Sneekop, 1557 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.17); Cederberg, Wupperthal Crystal Pools (-32.33, 19.14); Lambert's Bay (-32.17, 18.32); Sawadee (-32.34, 18.99).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dweller found in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threat and the species receives protection in several areas, such as the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016), Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2015) and Leggalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011).

Figs 1–10. *Langona hirsuta*. 1–4. Female from Otters Den. 5. Female in alcohol. 6. Male in alcohol. 7, 8. Epigyne. 9–11. Male palp. Credits: 1–4. Wynand Uys. 5, 6, 8, 11. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2011). 7, 9, 10. Charles Haddad.

Langona lotzi Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011

COMMON NAME: Lotz's Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2011 from the Golden Gate Highlands National Park in the Free State. The species is known from South Africa and Lesotho. In South Africa, it is known from the Free State, Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal (EOO=15 499 km²; AOO=40 km²; 522–2700 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small distribution range (< 20 000 km²), it is regarded as Vulnerable.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.50, 28.87); Wynford Guest Farm (-28.80, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Sani Pass 900 m (-30.20, 30.40); Sani Pass 1800 m (-29.68, 29.51); Sani Pass 2100 m (-29.62, 29.44); Sani Pass 2400 m (-29.66, 29.51); Sani Pass 2700 m (-29.65, 29.44). **Mpumalanga:** Secunda (-26.55, 29.17).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dweller sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013). Some specimens were collected by pitfall trapping where they occur abundantly in montane grasslands in southern KwaZulu-Natal from altitudes ranging from 900–2700 m a.s.l..

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a small range but is protected in the Golden Gate Highlands National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024) and Giant's Castle Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011).

Figs 1–11. *Langona lotzi*. 1–4 Immature male from Secunda. 5–6. Male from Wyndford. 7. Female. 8. Male. 9. Epigyne. 10, 11. Male palp. Credits: 1–4. Robert Wienand. 5–6. Peter Webb. 7–9, 11. After Haddad & Wesolowska (2011). 10. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Langona manicata Simon, 1901

COMMON NAME: Makapan Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1901 from Makapan (EOO=<math><100\text{ km}^2</math>; AOO=8 km²; 1038 m a.s.l.). The species is known from two provinces. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female, re-describe the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Makapan (-25.23, 28.11). *North West*: Potchefstroom (-26.70, 27.09).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling spider known from the Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) Biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: This very rare species is undersampled and known only from two localities. More sampling is needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Only known from the male (Simon, 1901).

Langona tortuosa Wesolowska, 2011

COMMON NAME: Namibian Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2011 from Namibia. Recorded from four southern African countries. In South Africa, it is known from Limpopo and Mpumalanga (EOO=9 602 km²; AOO=20 km²; 230–1486 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Balloon (-24.20, 30.34); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm The Downs (-24.14, 30.31); Vhembe Biosphere, Buzzard Mountain (-23.00, 29.77); Soutpansberg Conservancy (-23.21, 29.51). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Satara (-24.38, 31.78); Kruger National Park, Satara, N'wanetsi (-24.44, 31.88).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling spider that is apparently widespread in moist and dry savannas in the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Presently protected in two protected areas: Kruger National Park and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska, 2011).

Figs 1–9. *Langona tortuosa*. 1–3. Female from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. 4. Male in alcohol. 5. Female in alcohol. 6, 7. Epigyne. 8, 9. Male palp. Credits: 1–3. Peter Webb. 4–9. From Wesolowska (2011).

Langona warchalowskii Wesolowska, 2007

COMMON NAME: Warchalowski's Langona Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2007 from Tierberg in the Western Cape. Sampled from three southern African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from seven provinces, including six protected areas (E₀₀=504 168 km²; A₀₀=68 km²; 243–1399 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77). **Gauteng:** Pretoria, Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Midlands, Boston, Good Hope plantation (-29.65, 29.97). **Limpopo:** Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.37, 29.32); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.30, 24.81); Griquatown district, Farm Bingap (-28.91, 22.99); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44)*. **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg, Niewoudt's Pass (-32.35, 19.01); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); 25 km E Prince Albert, Tierberg (-33.17, 22.28); Table Mountain National Park (-33.90, 18.38)*.

LIFESTYLE: An exclusively ground-dwelling spider collected primarily with pitfall traps. Sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011), Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is conserved in several protected areas, including the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2019), Benfontein Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2019), Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016) and Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska, 2007).

Figs 1–10. *Langona warchalowskii*. 1–3. Female from Tswalu Game Reserve. 4. Male in alcohol. 5. Male from Tswalu Game Reserve. 6. Male line drawing. 7–8. Epigyne. 9–10. Male palp. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4, 6, 7, 8, 10. After Haddad & Wesolowska (2011). 5. Peter Webb. 9. Charles Haddad.

GENUS *LEPTORCHESTES* Thorell, 1870

Leptorchestes Thorell, 1870 is a small genus known from seven species, of which six occur in the Mediterranean and only a single Afrotropical species, *L. separatus* Wesołowska & Szeremeta, 2001 from Namibia, has been described to date (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Ant-like Jumping Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Leptorchestes berolinensis* (C.L. Koch, 1846)

MORPHOLOGY: Slender ant-like spiders with long legs, total length <5 mm. Carapace black or dark brown, with sparse black setae; carapace subrectangular, rounded posteriorly, with sides almost parallel, without constriction; convex in lateral view, thoracic part slightly higher than cephalic region; anterior and middle eyes close together. Abdomen with distinct pedicel; pear-shaped, with deep constriction near middle of abdomen; dark and decorated with transverse white band in constriction. Legs long and slender, III or IV longest; legs dark, frequently decorated with paler longitudinal stripes. Female slightly larger than male but abdomen less slender, with similar markings to male.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dwellers associated with ants. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Desert biomes.

TAXONOMY: Although no described species have been recorded from South Africa, single specimens have been recorded from three localities, Richtersveld National Park (-28.18, 17.04), Hopefield farm, Bloemfontein district (-28.85, 26.15) and Malmesbury (-33.45, 18.72).

Figs 1–7. *Leptorchestes* species from South Africa: 1–2. Female from Malmesbury; 3–5. Male from Richtersveld National Park. 6, 7. Subadult female from Hopefield farm, Bloemfontein district. 1, 2, 5, 7. Lateral habitus; 3, 6. Dorsal habitus; 4. Male palp. Credits: 1–2. Cecile Roux. 3–7. Charles Haddad.

GENUS *MANZUMA* Azarkina, 2020

The genus *Manzuma* Azarkina, 2020 is known from seven species (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Manzuma jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Manzuma nigritibiis* (Caporiacco, 1941)

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders, ranging in body length from 2.80 to 3.75 mm in males and 3.80 to 4.60 mm in females. The body shape of *Manzuma* is very similar to that of *Aelurillus* Simon, 1884, but *Manzuma* differs from *Aelurillus* in the genital characters. Sexes similar in general body shape but males usually smaller and more brightly coloured. Colour pattern of both sexes usually with two longitudinal stripes running along the anterior lateral eyes to posterior lateral eye lines, continuing posteriorly (poorly visible or invisible in some females); the anterior part of the eye field is covered with short erect bristles called 'rod hairs'. Abdomen elongate, without scutum; markings simple, with white median longitudinal stripe in males and usually with two median longitudinal lines of white spots in females. Legs subequal in length; femora of legs III longer than others.

LIFESTYLE: *Manzuma* species are ground-dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Two species have been recorded from South Africa (Azarkina, 2020).

Figs 1, 2. *Manzuma botswana* male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. Credit: Vida van der Walt

Figs 3, 4. *Manzuma petroae* female (3) and male (4). Credit: Vida van der Walt

Manzuma botswana Azarkina, 2020

COMMON NAME: Botswana Manzuma Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2020 from Maxwee in the Okavango Delta, Botswana. It has also been recorded from South Africa (EEO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1245 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.19, 30,33).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dwellers sampled from savanna.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to determine the species range in South Africa. It receives some protection in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Both sexes are known. Clypeus covered with short brown scales, with central transverse stripe of white hairs. Cheeks with two stripes of white scales running from ALEs to the lateral sides of carapace. Femur I without dense long yellow-white hairs prolaterally (Azarkina, 2020).

Figs 1–10. *Manzuma botswana*. 1–4. Male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. 5, 6. Male in alcohol. 7, 8. Female in alcohol. 9. Epigyne. 10. Male palp. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4. Peter Webb. 5–10. From Azarkina (2019).

Manzuma petroae Azarkina, 2020

COMMON NAME: Petro's Manzuma Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2020 from KwaZulu-Natal. In South Africa, it has been recorded from five provinces (EOO=206,046 km²; AOO=40 km²; 320–1315 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Fort Beaufort, Mpofo Nature Reserve (-32.60, 26.59); Queenstown/Komani, Sandringham (-31.90, 26.88)*. **Gauteng:** Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Pretoria/ Tshwane, Rietondale Research Campus (-25.73, 28.22); Roodepoort, Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden (-26.14, 27.86). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hluhluwe-Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.21, 31.95); Ithala Game Reserve, Doornkraal Camp (-27.51, 31.20). **Limpopo:** Settlers, Tweekansen (-25.48, 28.56); Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte (-24.90, 28.73). **North-West:** 40 km NW of Brits (-25.63, 27.78).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dwellers that are easily sampled with pitfall traps.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats. It receives some protection in the Mpofo Nature Reserve, Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden, Ithala Game Reserve and Hluhluwe/Umfolozi Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Clypeus and cheeks covered with long white hairs; clypeus with diamond-shaped patch of brown hairs between anterior median eyes and on upper half of clypeus. Femur I prolaterally with dense long yellow-white hairs (Azarkina, 2020).

Figs 1–8. *Manzuma petroae*. 1–4. Male. 5, 6. Female. 7. Male palp. 8. Epigyne. Credits: 1–3, 5, 6. Vida van der Walt. 4, 7, 8. From Azarkina (2020).

GENUS *MASSAGRIS* Simon, 1900

The genus *Massagris* Simon, 1900 is known from eight species (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Massagris Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Massagris constricta* Simon, 1900, the type species, is a *nomen dubium* (cf. Wesolowska, 1993: 140).

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders, length about 5 mm. This genus is recognised by the posterior lateral eyes that are situated closer to the anterior lateral eyes. The carapace is slightly elongated with dark spots around the eyes; rather convex, declining behind eye field; square eye field occupies about half of cephalothorax length; eyes of second row situated near anterior lateral eyes, contrasting from other Salticidae. Abdomen elongate-oval; spinnerets small, placed at tip of abdomen. Legs moderately long and slender, femora of first and second pairs a little thicker; legs almost the same length. Male pedipalp fairly large, tibia with single apophysis, bulbus very convex, embolus composed of two parts. Epigyne oval, medium-sized, weakly sclerotized, with two rather large shallow depressions.

LIFESTYLE: Specimens are found in leaf litter and low-growing vegetation.

TAXONOMY: Six species have been recorded from South Africa (Wesolowska, 1993; Wesolowska and Haddad, 2013, 2018).

Figs 1–3. 1. Male, lateral view. 2. Line drawing of the eye pattern. 3. Carapace. Credits: 1. Wanda Wesolowska. 2. Wesolowska (1993); 3. Cecile Roux.

Massagris honesta Wesolowska, 1993

COMMON NAME: Cape Massagris Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1993 from Cape Town. Sampled in South Africa from two provinces (EOO=123 322 km²; AOO=104 km²; 7–1307 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Camdeboo Local Municipality (-32.07, 24.12)*; Colchester (-33.69, 25.81)*; Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW Cape St Francis (-34.20, 24.70). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Darling (-33.37, 18.39); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Elgin (-34.16, 19.06); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Fisherhaven (-34.36, 19.13); Garden Route National Park, Slakplaas (-33.96, 22.09)*; George (-33.95, 22.46); Grootvadersbosch Forest Station (-34.00, 20.78); Grootvadersbosch Nature Reserve (-33.98, 20.82); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-34.01, 18.41); Marloth Nature Reserve (-34.25, 20.57); Mosselbay (-34.05, 21.89)*; Napier (-34.48, 19.91)*; Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Swellendam (-34.02, 20.42); Table Mountain National Park, Orange Kloof (-34.08, 18.24); Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38); Vermont (-34.40, 19.15); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

LIFESTYLE: *Massagris honesta* was found in leaf litter and low-growing vegetation in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Thicket and Forest biomes in southern South Africa. At De Hoop, it was sampled on a rocky shore with retreats made in the intertidal zone.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats and the species is conserved in several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Wesolowska (1993) and the male and female were redescribed by Wesolowska and Haddad (2013), with notes added by Prószyński (2017).

Figs 1–11. *Massagris honesta*. 1, 2. Female, dorsal. 3. Female, anterior view. 4. Female in alcohol. 5. Male in alcohol. 6, 7. Epigyne. 8–11. Male palp. Credits: 1, 3. Vida van der Walt. 2, 4, 5, 7, 10, 11. Charles Haddad. 6, 8, 9. From Wesolowska and Haddad (2013).

Massagris maculosa Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018

COMMON NAME: Spotted Massagris Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic species described in 2018 from Outeniquastrand near George. Known only from the type locality (EOO=100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 100 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* George, Outeniquastrand (-34.04, 22.28).

LIFESTYLE: A ground-dwelling species collected from the base of grass tussocks, between leaf litter and rocks in coastal thicket in the Fynbos Biome (Wesolowska and Haddad, 2018).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Known only from the Western Cape; more sampling is needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Both sexes known (Wesolowska and Haddad, 2018).

Figs 1–5. *Massagris maculosa*. 1. Female. 2. Male. 3, 4. Epigyne. 5. Male palp. Credits: From Wesolowska and Haddad (2018).

Massagris mirifica G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Massagris Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1903 from Durban. Sampled from three provinces and protected in seven protected areas (EOO=232 404 km²; AOO=56 km²; 5–1307 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Bestershoek Nature Reserve (-32.71, 25.57); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve (-32.68, 26.49); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.04, 24.94); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Gwala-Gwala Forest (-28.38, 32.40); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: The species was collected using canopy fogging and beating, primarily in Afromontane and coastal forests in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024) and Forest biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threats to the species and it is presently conserved in seven protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: *Massagris mirifica*, described from the male, is the senior synonym of *M. contortuplicata* Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013, which was described from the female; the species were synonymized after being recorded together at several localities (Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018).

Figs 1–5. *Massagris mirifica*. 1. Male in alcohol. 2. Female in alcohol. 3–4. Male palp. 5. Epigyne. Credits: From Wesolowska and Haddad (2018).

Massagris natalensis Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009

COMMON NAME: Natal Massagris Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2009 from Ndumo Game Reserve. Presently known only from four protected areas (EEO=13 368 km²; AOO=16 km²; 8–839 m a.s.l.), with several possible additional localities based on photographic records. The status of the species remains obscure and some more sampling is needed to determine its range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ithala Nature Reserve, Ntshodwe Camp (-27.54, 31.28); Ithala Nature Reserve, Doornkraal Camp (-27.51, 31.20); Ladysmith (-28.54, 29.78)*; Mtunzini (-28.96, 31.75)*; Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). *Limpopo:* Blyde River near Hoedspruit (-24.40, 30.81)*.

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dwelling species found in leaf litter and low-growing vegetation. It was collected from beneath rocks and logs in the Savanna Biome where it is well camouflaged against the substrate (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats but the species is only known from a small area. However, it is protected in three reserves.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Wesolowska and Haddad (2009) and the female by Wesolowska and Haddad (2018).

Figs 1–11. *Massagris natalensis*. 1–3. Female from Ndumo. 4. Male from Hoedspruit. 5–6. Male. 7. Epigyne. 8. Palp. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4. Wynand Uys. 5–8. After Wesolowska and Haddad (2013).

Massagris schisma Maddison & Zhang, 2006

COMMON NAME: Oorlogkloof Massagris Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 2006 from the Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve. The species is only known from the type locality (EOO=100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 738 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve (-31.40, 19.15).

LIFESTYLE: Found in leaf litter and low-growing vegetation in the Succulent Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: According to Prószyński (2017), *M. schisma* is misplaced.

Massagris schisma Maddison & Zhang, 2006

Figs 1–5. *Massagris mirifica*. 1. Male, dorsal view. 2. Male, ventral view. 3, 4. Male palp. 5. Eye pattern. Credits: 1–3. A. Dippenaar–Schoeman. 4, 5. From Maddison and Zhang (2006).

Massagris separata Wesolowska, 1993

COMMON NAME: Kirkwood Massagris Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described in 1993 from the Blue Cliff in Kirkwood. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO=100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 133 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Blue Cliff, Kirkwood (-33.50, 25.47).

LIFESTYLE: Found in leaf litter and low-growing vegetation in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Wesolowska, 1993).

Figs 1–2. *Massagris separata*. 1. Palp. 2. Eye pattern. Credit: From Wesolowska (1993).

GENUS *MELEON* Wanless, 1984

The genus *Meleon* Wanless, 1894 is known from eight species (World Spider Catalog, 2025), with three species from continental Africa and three from Madagascar.

COMMON NAME: Meleon jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Meleon kenti* (Lessert, 1925)

MORPHOLOGY: Medium-sized spiders (i.e. between 4.0 and 8.0 mm in length). Carapace high, usually with an abrupt anterior slope from about level of posterior median eyes to anterior eye row, gradually sloping from posterior eyes to rear of carapace; longer than broad. Eyes: set on moderately low tubercles; anterior eyes subcontiguous or closely spaced, weakly to strongly recurved in frontal view; anterior medians largest; posterior medians large, positioned slightly nearer to and on or slightly inside optical axis of anterior laterals; posterior lateral eyes slightly smaller or as large as anterior laterals, situated inside lateral margins of carapace when viewed from above; clypeus: moderately high, similar to diameter of anterior median eyes; moderately robust, more or less parallel and slightly inclined anteriorly; fang moderately robust and curved; promargin with three teeth, retro-margin with three to six. Abdomen generally elongate ovoid. Legs long and slender, with numerous moderately strong spines; legs I sometimes with strong fan like fringes on venter and dorsum of tibiae, venter of femora and to a lesser extent on venter of patellae; also, legs II and IV sometimes with a ventral fringe, more or less limited to the tibial apices. Female palps: moderately long, rather slender with apical claw.

LIFESTYLE: They inhabit leaf litter, forest understories, and tree trunks, often in humid tropical environments across mainland Africa and Madagascar.

TAXONOMY: The genus has undergone multiple reclassifications. Only *Meleon kenti* is reported from South Africa (Wanless, 1984). They resemble *Portia schultzi* but in *Meleon kenti* last two segments of the front legs are shorter and slightly thicker.

Figs 1–2. *Meleon kenti* females. 1. Eye pattern. 2. Carapace lateral view. Credits: 1. Bruce Blake. 2. From Wanless (1984).

Meleon kenti (Lessert, 1925)

COMMON NAME: Kent's Dandy Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described in 1925 as *Portia kenti* from Umbilo in KwaZulu-Natal. Recorded from four African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from three provinces (EOO=3 568 km²; AOO=20 km²; 17–496 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Malawi, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Umhlanga (-29.70, 31.09).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller mostly sampled by hand from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Widely distributed with no known threats. Protected in Kosi Bay Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Male described by Wanless (1978).

Figs 1–9. *Meleon kenti*. 1. Female anterior view. 2. Female dorsal view. 3. Carapace, lateral view. 4. Leg I. 5. Epigyne. 6–7. Male palp. Credits: 1–2. Vida van der Walt. 3–7. From Wanless (1978)

GENUS *MENEMERUS* Simon, 1868

The genus *Menemerus* Simon, 1868 is known from 36 species, most of which were described from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Menemerus Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Menemerus semilimbatus* (Hahn, 1829)

MORPHOLOGY: Medium to large jumping spiders, ranging from about 3 to 10 mm in length; body flattened, strongly hairy. Carapace with white lateral margins in the majority of species. Cephalothorax rather low, flat and broad, broadest in posterior half. Whole carapace clothed in short, dense brown and greyish-white hairs. Numerous long, brown bristles near eyes. Eye field rectangular or slightly trapezoid, wider than long. Abdomen oval, flattened, elongate in some species, rounded in others. Abdomen clothed in very bushy hairs, longer and denser at anterior edge. Venter usually light. Integument of abdomen often transparent, with numerous silver spots of internal guanine crystals. Legs rather short, generally light, sometimes banded. First pair of legs stronger than others.

LIFESTYLE: The biology of *Menemerus* species is poorly known. From scanty information on collecting labels, one can infer that some species are terrestrial, as they were collected in pitfall traps on the ground on sandy plains. Some were caught in low vegetation. There are records of some species being captured on tree trunks (*M. minshullae* and *M. transvaalicus*) or on stone walls or the walls of buildings (*M. bivittatus*, *M. bifurcus*, *M. rubicundus*, *M. transvaalicus* and *M. natalis*). Some species were also found inside houses. Wesolowska (1999) reported the presence of a stridulatory apparatus of the chelicera-palpal femur type in males of five African species: *M. bivittatus*, *M. brevibulbis*, *M. congoensis*, *M. eburnensis* and *M. fagei*.

TAXONOMY: The genus is quite distinctive, but morphologically rather uniform, making it easy to distinguish from other genera. However, species identification within the genus is fairly difficult. The genus was revised by Wesolowska (1999), with additions by Wesolowska (2006).

Menemerus bifurcus (Vida van der Walt)

Menemerus bivittatus (Vida van der Walt)

Menemerus carlini (John Richter)

Menemerus eburnensis (Vida van der Walt)

Menemerus fagei (Vida van der Walt)

Menemerus lesserti (Vida van der Walt)

QUICK GUIDE GENUS *MENEMERUS* Simon, 1868

Menemerus bifurcus male (Vida van der Walt) and female (Cecile Roux)

Menemerus bifurcus Wesolowska, 1999

Menemerus eburnensis female (Vida van der Walt) and drawing of male abdomen (From Wesolowska, 1999)

Menemerus eburnensis Berland & Millot, 1941

Menemerus bivittatus female (Vida van der Walt) and male (Peter Webb)

Menemerus bivittatus Dufour, 1831

Menemerus fagei female (Vida van der Walt) and male (Andrew Deacon)

Menemerus fagei Berland & Millot, 1941

Menemerus carlini female (Wynand Uys) and male (Robert Taylor)

Menemerus carlini Peckham & Peckham, 1903

Menemerus foordi male (From Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024)

Menemerus foordi Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024

Menemerus congoensis female (From Wesolowska, 1999)

Menemerus congoensis Lessert, 1927

Menemerus lesnei male (From Wesolowska, 1999)

Menemerus lesnei Lessert, 1936

GENUS *MENEMERUS* Simon, 1868

Menemerus lesserti female and male (Vida van der Walt)

Menemerus pilosus male (Charles Haddad).

Menemerus meridionalis

Menemerus rubicundus female (Charles Haddad)

Menemerus minshallae female (Peter Webb) and male (Robert Wienand)

Menemerus transvaalicus female (Vida van der Walt) and male (John Wilkinson)

Menemerus natalis male (Robert Wienand)

Menemerus zimbabweensis female and male (Vida van der Walt)

Menemerus bifurcus Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Zambian Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described in 1999 from Zambia, now with a pantropical distribution. In South Africa, it has been recorded from five provinces (EOO=161 219 km²; AOO=40 km²; 534–1415 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Pantropical species, widely introduced to tropical and subtropical areas in many parts of the world. In Africa, it is known from Mozambique, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). **Gauteng:** Baviaanspoort (-25.67, 28.37); Ferndale, Randburg (-26.09, 27.98)*; Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Mooikloof (-25.84, 28.33)*; Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.64, 28.36); Sandton (-26.06, 28.07); Wallmannsthal (-25.52, 28.30). **Limpopo:** Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Tshipise (-22.60, 30.16); Tzaneen (-23.83, 30.16); Waterberg (-24.48, 28.69)*. **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Potchefstroom (-26.7, 27.09); Rustenburg (-25.69, 27.14)*; Welgegund (-23.83, 27.95). **Western Cape:** Riebeeck West (-33.34, 18.86)*.

LIFESTYLE: The species has been sampled from buildings and gardens, where it lives on trees and in leaf litter. In South Africa, it has been sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). It was also found in cotton fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Wide distribution with no known threats.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska, 1999).

Figs 1–7. *Menemerus bifurcus*. 1–2. Male from Pretoria. 3. Male from Tshipise. 4. Female. 5. Epigyne. 6. Male palpal femur. 7. Male palp. Credits: 1–2. Vida van der Walt. 3. John Wilkinson. 4. Cecile Roux. 5–7. From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus bivittatus (Dufour, 1831)

COMMON NAME: Grey wall jumping spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A pantropical species described in 1831 as *Salticus bivittatus*. Recorded throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known from six provinces (EOO=604 218 km²; AOO=72 km²; 7–1382 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Introduced to North, Central and South America, St. Helena, southern Europe, Turkey, India, China, Taiwan, Japan, Vietnam, Australia and some Pacific islands. Widely distributed throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Fish River Mouth (-32.50, 27.17); Gqeberha, Miramar (-33.99, 25.54)*; Hankey (-33.75, 24.58)*; Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kirkwood (-33.38, 25.45)*. **Gauteng:** Johannesburg, Lyndhurst (-26.12, 28.10); Moreleta Kloof Nature Reserve (-25.81, 28.29)*; Pretoria, Lynnwood (-25.75, 28.25)*. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ballito (-29.43, 31.22); Durban (-29.85, 31.01)*; Empangeni, Fairview (-28.75, 31.90)*; Scottsburgh (-30.28, 30.75); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22). **Limpopo:** Mopani District (-23.84, 30.15)*; Phalaborwa (-23.94, 31.14)*. **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Bushbuckridge (-24.45, 31.97)*; Mbombela (-25.47, 30.97)*. **Western Cape:** Bergrivier (-33.06, 19.03)*; Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42)*; De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Fisherhaven (-34.47, 19.27); George (-33.95, 22.46); Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Gardens (-33.99, 18.43); Knysna (-34.01, 23.03)*; Lamberts Bay (-32.10, 18.31); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Paternoster (-32.81, 17.89)*; Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Swellendam (-34.03, 20.52)*; Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48)*; Van Rhynsdorp (-31.84, 18.63)*; Wellington (-33.65, 19.00); Worcester (-33.60, 19.47).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller recorded from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes in South Africa. Commonly found on the outside walls of houses, especially in the coastal provinces.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Wide distribution with no known threats.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes; revised by Wesolowska (1999).

Figs 1–9. *Menemerus bivittatus*. 1. Male from Jeffrey's Bay. 2, 3. Female from Cape Town. 4, 5. Male. 6. Epigyne. 7. Male palp. 8, 9. Abdomens. Credits: 1. Charles Haddad. 2–5. Vida van der Walt. 6–9. From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus carlini (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)

COMMON NAME: Carlin’s Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1903 as *Mendoza carlinii* from Zimbabwe. Recorded from two African countries. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces (EOO=3 178 km²; AOO=16 km²; 280–565 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bathurst, Pigs Island (-33.50, 26.84); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Kentani (-32.50, 28.32); Stutterheim (-32.69, 27.61)*. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Richmond (-29.83, 30.31)*. **Limpopo:** Blyde River, near Hoedspruit (-24.40, 30.81)*; Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.75).

LIFESTYLE: The species is found on hard, smooth vertical surfaces such as smooth-barked tree trunks, rock faces, tall concrete poles and house walls. Sampled from the Savanna and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide distribution with no known threats.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: This is a flat gray species with a light, foliated abdominal band. In the male, the cephalothorax has a dark background, with reddish hairs on the sides and distinct bright red hairs around the eyes. The band around the margin and across the clypeus is pure white, and there is a cluster of white hairs at the insertion of the falces. In the female, the cephalothorax is black, with a snow-white band around the margin and a longitudinal white band on the thoracic part. The abdomen is black with a wide longitudinal, foliated band of mixed white and red hairs (Wesołowska, 1999).

Figs 1–8. *Menemerus carlini*. 1, 2. Female from Hoedspruit. 3, 4. Male, showing red setae below eyes. 5. Male. 6, 7. Female. 8. Epigyne. 9. Male palp. Credits: 1, 2. Wynand Uys. 3, 4. Robert Taylor. 5, 6, 9. From Peckham & Peckham (1903). 7. Charles Haddad. 8. From Wesołowska (1999).

Menemerus congoensis Lessert, 1927

COMMON NAME: Congo Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1927 from Zaire (D.R. Congo). It has a wide distribution from Ethiopia to South Africa. In South Africa, it is presently known from only two localities in Gauteng (EEO=1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 224–1264 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in Africa, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: A widely distributed Afrotropical species; reported from Ethiopia to South Africa, but not from West Africa: D.R. Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Namibia, Rwanda, South Africa and Zambia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Gauteng: Wallmansthal (-25.52, 28.30); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19).

LIFESTYLE: Some specimens have been hand collected in grass tussocks and on rocks in the Grassland Biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Widely distributed in Africa with no known threats.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Wesolowska (1999) revised the genus and both sexes are known. This species is closely related to *M. eburnensis*.

Figs 1–5. *Menemerus congoensis*. 1. Male habitus. 2. Female abdomen. 3. Epigyne. 4, 5. Male palp. Credits: From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus eburnensis Berland & Millot, 1941

COMMON NAME: Ivory Coast Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1941 from the Ivory Coast. Presently known from three African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from two provinces (EEO=24 228 km²; AOO=20 km²; 894–1245 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in Africa, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, Senegal, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria/Tshwane, Krauseville (-25.73, 28.02)*; Tswaing Nature Reserve (-25.41, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Balloon (-24.20, 30.34). **Mpumalanga:** Mbombela (-25.42, 30.99)*.

LIFESTYLE: Specimens in South Africa have been sampled with pitfall traps in the Savanna biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is recorded from three protected areas in South Africa: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016) and Tswaing Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2025).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Wesolowska (1999) revised the genus and both sexes are known.

Figs 1–9. *Menemerus eburnensis*. 1–3. Female from Irene. 4, 5. Epigyne. 6. Male palp. 7, 8. Female abdominal patterns. 9. Male abdomen. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4, 6–9. After Wesolowska (1999). 5. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Menemerus fagei Berland & Millot, 1941

COMMON NAME: Fage's Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1941 from Burkino Faso. The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces, including two protected areas (EOO=111 415 km²; AOO=20 km²; 150–1158 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Burkina Faso, Chad, Djibouti, Egypt, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Mali, Niger, Senegal, South Africa, Sudan, Togo and Yemen.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng:* Wallmannsthal (-25.52, 28.30). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Jozini (-27.42, 32.07). *Limpopo:* Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Malelane (-25.49, 31.50)*; Sabi Sands (-24.75, 31.37). *Mpumalanga:* Mbombela (-25.47, 30.97)*.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers sampled by hand and pitfall traps from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: A species with a wide distribution and no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019) and Kruger National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesolowska (1999). Known from both sexes.

Menemerus fagei Berland & Millot, 1941

Figs 1–9. *Menemerus fagei*. 1, 2. Female from Sabi Sand. 3. Female from Malelane. 4. Abdomen. 5, 6. Epigyne. 7–9. Palp. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3. Andrew Deacon. 4–9. From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus foordi Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024

COMMON NAME: Foord's Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described from the Northern Cape. The species is only known from the type locality (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=8 km²; 537–645 m a.s.l.).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Richtersveld National Park, Akkedis Pass (-28.17, 17.03); Richtersveld National Park, Kokerboomkloof (-28.31, 17.27).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living hunter sampled from grasses and rocks in the Desert Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is known only from the male. More sampling is needed to discover the female and determine the species' range, but it is protected in the Richtersveld National Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2025). As such, it is considered Data Deficient.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Carapace dark brown, eye field black, with wide streaks composed of white hairs along lateral margins. Clypeus with white hairs. Abdomen black, with broad white streaks laterally, venter dark brown, spinnerets black. Legs brown, hairy. Palps dark brown, femur and tibia clothed in white hairs (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024).

Menemerus foordi Haddad & Wesolowska, 2024

Figs 1–5. *Menemerus foordi*. 1. Male, dorsal habitus. 2. Subadult male, dorsal habitus. 3. Same, anterior view. 4, 5. Male palp. Credits: 2–3. Vida van der Walt 1, 4, 5. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2024).

Menemerus lesnei Lessert, 1936

COMMON NAME: Lesne's Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1936 from Mozambique. The species is known from five African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from two provinces, including two protected areas (EOO=1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 91–588 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Western Cape:* Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Fynbos biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide range in southern Africa and there are no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in the Tembe Elephant Park and Swartberg Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Clypeus low, with a few white hairs. Chelicerae and labium brown, maxillae brown with yellow margins, sternum yellowish-brown. Abdomen generally dark, brownish-grey, medially somewhat lighter, with traces of wide russet stripe anteriorly. Delicate brown hairs cover abdomen, hairs only longer and denser at anterior margin. Venter yellowish. Legs: leg I slightly longer and thicker than the rest, femur almost black with few white hairs dorsally at distal end, patella and tibia dark brown, metatarsus and tarsus paler; legs II–IV yellowish-orange; legs with long, thin, brown hairs. Pedipalp: brown, clothed in dense brown hairs, white hairs only distally on femur (Wesołowska, 1999).

Figs 1–3. *Menemerus lesnei*. 1. Habitus, lateral view. 2. Male palp. 3. Male palpal femur. Credits: From Wesołowska (1999).

Menemerus lesserti Lawrence, 1927

COMMON NAME: Lessert's Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1927 from Namibia. Recorded from three African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from the Limpopo and Northern Cape provinces (EOO=168 995 km²; AOO=20 km²; 35–1077 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in southern Africa, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Groblersdal, Farm Moosrivier (-25.16, 29.39); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Tshipise (-22.60, 30.16); **North-ern Cape:** Richtersveld National Park, near Hand of God (-28.10, 16.91); Richtersveld National Park, Sendelingsdrif Research Accommodation (-28.12, 16.89).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Savanna and Desert biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2025).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Wide distribution range with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve and Richtersveld National Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2025).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Wesolowska (1999).

Figs 1–11. *Menemerus lesserti*. 1, 2. Female from Sabi Sands. 3, 4. Male from Sabi Sands. 5. Female in alcohol. 6. Male in alcohol. 7, 8. Epigyne. 9. Male palpal femur. 10, 11. Male palp. Credits: 1–4. Vida van der Walt. 5, 6. Charles Haddad. 8, 9, 11. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2024). 7, 10. From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus meridionalis Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Dendron Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD /Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described in 1999 from Dendron in Limpopo. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1025 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.37, 29.32).

LIFESTYLE: The species was sampled by beating *Acacia tortilis* trees (Dippenaar–Schoeman, 2025). Sampled in the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Carapace flattened, dark brown, eye field almost black. Long brown bristles near eyes. White lines composed of hairs along lateral margins of carapace. White hairs scattered sparsely on carapace. Abdomen with very wide dark brown median streak, sides covered with white hairs. Venter with wide brownish stripe. Long and dense brown hairs at anterior abdominal margin. Spinnerets brown. Legs light brown, leg hairs brown (Wesolowska, 1999). Known from only the male.

Figs 1–2. *Menemerus meridionalis*, male palp. From: Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus minshullae Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Minshull's Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1999 from Zimbabwe. Recorded from three African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from two provinces, including four protected areas (EOO=23 133 km²; AOO=20 km²; 47–1341 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Malawi, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Limpopo:* Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Hoedspruit (-24.35, 30.95)*; Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.44); Western Soutpansberg, Little Leigh (-22.94, 29.87).

LIFESTYLE: The species was sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011). It was also found on the bark of the fever tree, *Vachellia xanthophloea*, in northern KwaZulu-Natal (Haddad, 2016).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threats to the species and it is protected in several reserves, including Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019), Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and the Soutpansberg Conservancy (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska, 1999).

Figs 1–10. *Menemerus minshullae*. 1. Female from Ndumo Game Reserve. 2–3. Male from Hoedspruit. 4. Female in alcohol. 5. Male in alcohol. 6. Abdominal pattern. 7, 8. Male palp. 9, 10. Epigyne. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2–3. Robert Wienand. 4, 5, 10. Charles Haddad. 6, 7, 9. From Wesolowska (1999). 8. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Menemerus natalis Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Natal Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1999 from Ashburton in KwaZulu-Natal. In South Africa, it has been sampled from two provinces (EOO=148 528 km²; AOO=24 km²; 17–1146 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ashburton (-29.68, 30.45); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Margate, Ramsgate Beach (-30.89, 30.34); Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.60, 32.02); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.88, 32.25); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umkomaas (-30.20, 30.80); uMgungundlovu District (-29.45, 30.27)*. *Limpopo:* Maasroom district, Farm Al-te-vêr (-22.75, 28.43); Western Soutpansberg, Farm Little Leigh (-22.94, 29.87).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from trees in the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011). One specimen was sampled from a silk retreat made under bark.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threats and the species is protected in the Tembe Elephant Park, Mkhuzi Game Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve and Soutpansberg Conservancy (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only the male is known (Wesolowska, 1999).

Figs 1–7. *Menemerus natalis*. 1–2. Male from Sabie Park. 3. Male from Pafuri. 4. Male from Westfalia. 5, 6. Male palp. 7. Male palpal femur. Credits: 1–4. Robert Wienand. 5–7. From Wesolowska (1999).

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Menemerus pilosus Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Hairy Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1999 from Namibia. Recorded from two African countries. In South Africa, it is only known from the Northern Cape (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 950 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from trees in the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Female unknown. The specific name is derived from the Latin word “pilos”, meaning hair, and refers to the very hairy body of this species. Carapace dark brown, eye field black. Whitish hairs cover carapace, especially numerous on eye field, brown bristles near eyes. White bands on lateral margins of carapace, clypeus with white hairs. Chelicerae, labium and sternum brown, maxillae brown with light margins. Abdomen dark brown medially and greyish laterally, covered with very dense hairs. Venter yellowish (Wesolowska, 1999).

Figs 1–6. *Menemerus pilosus*, male. 1. Dorsal habitus. 2. Ventral habitus. 3, 5, 6. Male palp. 4. Palpal femur. Credits: 1, 2, 5, 6. Charles Haddad. 3, 4. From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus rubicundus Lawrence, 1928

COMMON NAME: Namibia Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African species described in 1928 from Namibia. Recorded from South Africa for the first time in 2018 and known from two provinces (EOO=16 173 km²; AOO=12 km²; 1142–1359 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.03, 26.20); Luckhoff district, Farm Bankfontein (-30.07, 24.88). **Northern Cape:** Alexander Bay (-28.60, 16.48)*; Hartswater (-27.85, 24.81); Richtersveld National Park (-28.10, 16.91)*.

LIFESTYLE: A species predominantly sampled from rocks and large boulders, as well as the bark of trees, on which it is very well camouflaged. Sampled from the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide geographical range in the western half of southern Africa and has no known threats.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Described from the female (Wesołowska, 1999), with the new distribution data and the description of the male provided by Wesołowska & Haddad (2018).

Figs 1–7. *Menemerus rubicundus*. 1, 2. Females from Bankfontein. 3. Female in alcohol. 4. Male palp. 5–7. Epigynes. Credits: 1–3, 7. Charles Haddad. 4, 6. From Wesołowska & Haddad (2018). 5. From Wesołowska (1999).

Menemerus transvaalicus Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Transvaal Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1999 from Marrievale, Gauteng. Sampled from Lesotho and South Africa. It has been recorded from all the South African provinces except KwaZulu-Natal (EOO=951 797 km²; AOO=112 km²; 1–2066 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.57, 25.68); Drakensberg District, Farm Martindale (-30.859, 27.863)*; Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Queenstown (-31.89, 26.85); Tarkastad (-32.00, 26.26). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, Bain's Vlei (-29.06, 26.15); Bloemfontein district, Malspoort (-29.02, 26.41); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Harrismith (-28.27; 29.13); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); Koppies Dam Nature Reserve (-27.22, 25.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85; 25.93); Vredefort (-26.938, 27.271)*. **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Marievale Nature Reserve (-26.42, 28.46); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Springs (-26.25, 28.43). **Limpopo:** Lion Sands (-24.950, 31.517)*; Soutpansberg (-23.43, 30.07); Tshipise (-22.534, 30.670)*. **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **North West:** Diamantkuil (-27.25, 25.83). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.30, 24.81); Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park (-25.48, 20.24); Hanover (-30.901, 24.628)*. **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36; 21.69); Tankwa Karoo National Park (-32.24, 20.10).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living hunter sampled from under bark, *Eucalyptus* trees, under rocks and around houses in the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide distribution with no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in several reserves and national parks.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Wesolowska, 1999)

Figs 1–12. *Menemerus transvaalicus*. 1–3. Female from Lion Sands. 4, 5. Male from Tshipise. 6. Female in alcohol. 7. Female habitus. 8. Male in alcohol. 9, 10. Epigyne. 11–15. Male palp. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4. John Wilkinson. 5. Esther vd Westhuizen. 6, 8, 9, 11, 12. Charles Haddad. 7, 10, 13–15. From Wesolowska (1999).

Menemerus zimbabwensis Wesolowska, 1999

COMMON NAME: Zimbabwe Menemerus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1999 from Zimbabwe. Recorded from two African countries. In South Africa, it is known from six provinces (EOO=159 043 km²; AOO=40 km²; 47–1119 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Merrievale Nature Reserve (-26.31, 28.51). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umkhanyakude (-27.60, 32.04)*. **Limpopo:** Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.416, 26.750)*; Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Pafuri, Waller's Camp (-22.424, 30.911)*; Tshipise (-22.53, 30.67); Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.32). **Mpumalanga:** Crocodile River Gorge, 20 km East of Nelspruit (-25.32, 31.13); Sabi Sands (-25.120, 31.919)*. **Northern Cape:** Upington (-28.453, 21.265)*. **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living hunter sampled from under rocks and shrubs in the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011). In northern KwaZulu-Natal, it was sampled from the bark of fever trees (*Vachellia xanthophloea*) and in canopy fogging samples.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide distribution and no known threats. In South Africa, it is protected in several reserves and national parks, including the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019), Ndumo Game Reserve (Wesolowska and Haddad, 2009) and Soutpansberg Conservancy (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The species was described by Wesolowska (1999). The male was described by Wesolowska (2007) and Wesolowska and Haddad (2009) added additional notes.

Figs 1–11. *Menemerus zimbabwensis*. 1, 2. Female from Ndumo Game Reserve. 3–4. Male from Ndumo Game Reserve. 5, 6. Male from Tshipise. 7. Female from Tshipise. 8, 9. Male, dorsal habitus. 10. Male, lateral habitus. 11. Epigyne. 12–14. Male palp. Credits: 1–4. Vida van der Walt. 5–7. John Wilkinson. 8, 11, 14. From Wesolowska (2007). 9, 10, 12, 13. Charles Haddad.

GENUS *MEXCALA* G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1902

The genus *Mexcala* is known from 22 species (World Spider Catalog, 2026), of which four are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Mexcala jumping spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Mexcala rufa* Peckham & Peckham, 1902

MORPHOLOGY: *Mexcala* contains slender, medium-sized spiders with long thin legs, especially last pair. The majority of *Mexcala* species have similar coloration, namely the carapace is blackish and legs brown with black lines along the sides. Abdominal patterns variable, with yellow or orange spots and/or black bands or abdominal surface uniformly covered with dense yellow-orange setae. In all the South African species, the tip of the front legs is white, clearly visible when they run around with front legs held in the air.

LIFESTYLE: They are diurnal hunters, using their excellent eyesight to locate prey, which appears to consist exclusively of ants. Their hunting strategy involves attacking from behind or the side and biting the ant behind the head or occasionally on the legs or antennae. The spiders are mimics and their models are ants and mutillid wasps, called also velvet ants. Females of these wasps are wingless, ant-like in body shape, and covered in velvety hairs. *Mexcala* species resemble their models, especially in their size, body proportions and bright, contrasting abdominal patterns. Research has shown that *M. elegans* is a euryphagous specialist using a specialized ant-eating capture strategy in which prey specialization has evolved as a byproduct of risk aversion (“enemy-free space” hypothesis) (Pekár & Haddad, 2011).

TAXONOMY: The genus was revised by Wesołowska (2009).

Figs 1–6. *Mexcala* spp. 1, 2. *Mexcala elegans* (Vida van der Walt). 3, 4. *M. quadrimaculata* (3. Peter Webb, 4. Vida van der Walt). 5. *M. rufa* (Felix Riegel). 6. *M. rufa* (Cecile Roux).

Mexcala elegans Peckham & Peckham, 1903

COMMON NAME: Elegant Mexcala Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1902 from Zimbabwe. The species has been recorded from eight African countries. In South Africa, it is known from eight provinces (EOO=694 355km²; AOO=124 km²; 3–1768 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, eSwatini, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Port St Johns (-31.609, 29.512)*. **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (-26.20, 28.04); Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-25.36, 27.99); Pretoria/Tshwane, National Botanical Gardens (-25.74, 28.19); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-26.50, 28.25); Zwartkop Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Irene (-25.868, 28.217)*. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie's Camp (-27.58, 32.67); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Gwala-Gwala Forest (-28.39, 32.40); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Mission Rocks picnic site (-28.25, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.60, 32.02); Ithala Game Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24)*; Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola Nature Reserve (-27.35, 31.61); Richard's Bay (-28.77, 32.11); Sheffield Beach (-29.46, 31.26); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.54, 32.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Mtunzini (-28.959, 31.750)*; Empangeni (-28.759, 31.901)*; Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38)*. **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71)*; Letsitele (-23.88, 30.37); Mookgophong/Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Tshipise (-22.60, 30.16); Klaserie Private Game Reserve (-24.213, 31.03\$)*; Berg-en-dal Rest Camp, Kruger National Park (-25.425, 31.4508)*; Kruger National Park; Shingwedzi Camp (-23.109, 31.436)*; Maruleng (-24.395, 30.941)*; Bela-Bela (-24.819, 28.064)*; Sabie Park (-24.975, 31.481)*; Phalaborwa (-24.505, 30.896)*; Musina (-22.628, 30.119)*; Blouberg, Bochum(-22.823, 28.5175). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Kambeni (-25.15, 31.27); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.12, 31.23); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96)*; Phiring (-24.529, 30.700)*. **Northern Cape:** 50 km E Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Carnavon (-30.603, 22,127)*. **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Potchefstroom (-26.867, 27.362)*; Swartruggens (-25.644, 26.673)*. **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: The species was collected from the ground, low-growing plants, on bark and on the walls of houses. Published data and photographs on iNaturalist show them feeding on ants.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide range, with no known threats. Although the female has been collected, it remains undescribed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesolowska (2009).

Figs 1–10. *Mexcala elegans*. 1. Male from Lephalale. 2. Male from Tshipise. 3. Anterior view. 4. Small immature from Ndumo. 5. Female in alcohol. 6. Female abdomen. 7, 8. Epigyne. 9. Male abdomen. 10. Male palp. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. John Wilkinson. 3. Vida van der Walt. 4, 5, 8. Charles Haddad. 6, 7, 9, 10. From Wesolowska (2009).

***Mexcala elegans* Peckham & Peckham, 1903**

Figs 1–4. *Mexcala elegans*. 1. Male from Lephalale. 2, 3, 4. Females, showing colour variation in specimens from South Africa (2), Botswana (3) and Zambia (4). Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Vida van der Walt. 3, 4. Charles Haddad.

Figs 5–10. Various life stages of *Mexcala elegans* feeding on *Camponotus* spp. ants at Ndumo Game Reserve. 5. Male. 6. Female. 7–10. Juveniles. Credits: Charles Haddad.

Mexcala meridiana Wesolowska, 2009

COMMON NAME: Sabie Mexcala Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2009 from Sabie Reserve (EOO=1330 km²; AOO=12 km²; 349–830 m a.s.l.). The species is only known only three localities and its status remains obscure because the male is unknown. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Glen Alpine Dam (-23.19, 28.68); Selati Game Reserve (-22.02, 30.77). *Mpumalanga*: Sabie Reserve (-25.25, 31.50).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Recorded from two protected areas, Selati Game Reserve and Sabie Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Carapace brown, with darker eye field, eyes surrounded black. Carapace covered with short brown hairs, denser on ocular area. Abdomen bleached, brownish with black posterior margin. Venter dark, with two lighter streaks laterally. Legs light brown, femora darker, leg hairs dark. Epigyne with large shallow depression (Wesolowska, 2009).

Figs. 1–3. *Mexcala meridiana*. 1–2. Female from Glen Alpine Dam. 3. Epigyne. Credits: 1, 2. Vida van der Walt. 3. From Wesolowska, (2009).

Mexcala quadrimaculata (Lawrence, 1942)

COMMON NAME: Four-spotted Mexcala Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1942 as *Cosmophasis quadrimaculatus* from Njelele River Limpopo. Known from five African countries. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces (EOO=1 434 926 km²; AOO=20 km²; 47–925 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide range, it is considered as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Malawi, Mozambique, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Alldays, Mogalakwena River Lodge (-22.726, 28.775)*; Hoedspruit, Maruleng (-24.094, 30.835)*; Mapungubwe National Park (-22.188, 29.201)*; Marakele National Park (-24.429, 27.534)*; Musina district, Farm Rochdale (-22.54, 29.41); Njelele River (-22.33, 30.50); Steenbokpan (-23.71, 27.27). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.865, 31.030)*; Kruger National Park (-24.543, 30.664)*. **KwaZulu Natal:** Empangeni (-28.759, 31.9018)*; Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Mtunzini (-28.96, 31.75)*; Zinkwazi Beach (-29.286, 31.438)*.

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dweller sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011). This species mimics a carabid beetle of the genus *Craspedophorus* in its coloration and movements.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Wide range with no known threats, but the male still needs to be discovered and described.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesołowska (2009) but only female is known.

Figs 1–6. *Mexcala quadrimaculata*. 1. Female dorsal view. 2. Anterior view. 3. Female from Jozini. 4. Carabid beetle of the genus *Craspedophorus*. 5. Habitus line drawing. 6. Epigyne. Credits: 1–2 Vida van der Walt. 3. Peter Webb. 4. Ruan Booysen. 5, 6. From Wesołowska (2009).

Mexcala rufa Peckham & Peckham, 1902

COMMON NAME: Yellow Mexcala Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1902 from South Africa with the type locality only given as Cape Colony. Presently, the species is known from three southern African countries. In South Africa, it has been recorded from four provinces (EOO=879 778 km²; AOO=72 km²; 7–1147 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cradock (-32.15, 25.60)*; Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.221, 25.482)*; Pearston (-32.571, 25.203)*; Graaff Reinet (-32.13, 24.32)*. **Free State:** Luckhoff district, Farm Bankfontein (-30.07, 24.88). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park, Letaba (-23.83, 31.58). **Northern Cape:** Fraserburg (32.178, 21.197)*; Groblershoop, Farm Blackridge (-28.490, 22.324)*; Kamiesberg (-29.617, 17.800)*; Kgalagadi Transfontier Park, Twee Rivieren (-26.43, 20.26); Meerkat National Park (-30.69, 21.39); Nababeep, Jakkalswater Guest Farm (-29.62, 17.80); Near Griekwastad (-28.916, 23.409)*; Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Richtersveld National Park, Kokerboomkloof (-28.30, 17.29); Schmidtsdrift district, Farm Geel-koppies (-28.60, 24.33); Witsand Kalahari Nature Reserve (-28.55, 22.49). **North West:** Hu-hudi (-26.398, 24.326)*. **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Bitterfontein (-31.046, 18.264)*; Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Cederberg Tourist Park, Kromrivier (-32.53, 19.28); Gamkaskloof Nature Reserve (-33.35, 21.67); Laingsburg district, Wagendrift Lodge (-33.37, 20.94); Montagu (-33.81, 20.15); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.35, 20.49).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland, (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Nama Karoo, Succulent Karoo, Desert and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011). *Mexcala rufa* is a free-living ground-dweller that is frequently found around nests of *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ants, which they mimic (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Uys, 2025). They feed on their models as well as other ants but have not been observed feeding on other arthropod taxa.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide range in southern Africa, with no known threats. Although the female has been collected, it remains undescribed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Wesołowska (2009). Female unknown.

Figs 1–12. *Mexcala rufa*. 1. Male from Wolwekop Nature Reserve. 2. Female from Bitterfontein. 3. Male from Jakkalswater. 4. *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ant. 5, 6. Females feeding on *C. fulvopilosus*. 7. Female in alcohol. 8. Retreat under rock. 9. Male abdomen. 10. Male palp. 11. Epigyne. Credits: 1. Felix Riegel. 2. Cecile Roux. 3–4. Peter Webb. 5–8, 11. Charles Haddad. 9, 10. From Wesołowska (2009).

GENUS *MICROBIANOR* Logunov, 2000

The genus *Microbianor* Logunov, 2000 is known from nine species (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Microbianor Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Microbianor nigratarsus* Logunov, 2000.

MORPHOLOGY: Small unidentate spiders ranging from 1.90 to 2.80 mm in length. Sexes similar in general body form, but males differ in having the large abdominal scutum completely covering the dorsum. Carapace: rather high, always shagreened in both sexes; fovea present but poorly visible. Eyes: in three rows; anterior row clearly narrower (ca. 1.2 times) than posterior row; middle row midway between PLE and ALE; quadrangle length 62–71 % of carapace length. Legs: more or less subequally developed, but legs I usually stronger, with their femora swollen; dorsal and ventral rows of fringes on male tibia I poorly developed (virtually unmarked); leg formula I 1423 or 1432 in both sexes, legs II and III subequal in length. Abdomen: elongate to round; dorsum in males always completely covered with large scutum; dorsal markings consisting of narrow anterior white band and sometimes with pair of white spots (Logunov, 2000).

LIFESTYLE: Tiny beetle-like salticids collected from low-growing vegetation.

TAXONOMY: Three species recorded from South Africa.

Figs 1–3. *Microbianor furcatus* male from Centurion.
Credits: Peter Webb

Microbianor furcatus Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013

COMMON NAME: Sparkling Microbianor Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic species described in 2013 from the Free State National Botanical Gardens. The species is known from three provinces (EOO=7 556 km²; AOO=16 km²; 381–1414 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mount Coke State Forest (-32.99, 27.47). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.59, 26.42); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Centurion (-25.85, 28.16).

LIFESTYLE: A tiny beetle-like salticid resembling small ladybirds (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). They are collected from low-growing vegetation in the Grassland and Forest biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide range but is undersampled. It is likely overlooked by collectors due to its small size.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The male was described by Haddad & Wesolowska (2013) and the female by Wesolowska & Haddad (2018).

Microbianor furcatus Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013

Figs 1–12. *Microbianor furcatus*. 1–3. Female. 4, 6. Male in alcohol. 5. Female in alcohol. 7. Male. 8, 9. Male leg I. 10, 11. Male palp. 12. Epigyne. Credits: 1–3. Vida van der Walt. 4, 5, 8, 10. Charles Haddad. 6, 9, 11, 12. From Wesolowska and Haddad (2018). 7. Peter Webb.

Microbianor globosus Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011

COMMON NAME: Striped Microbianor Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 2011 from the Green Valley Nuts Estate in Prieska (EOO=100 km²; AOO=8 km²; 950–1193 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Witsand Kalahari Nature Reserve (-28.56, 22.48).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground wanderer. Collected from the base of grass tussocks on the banks of the Orange River in the Nama Karoo Biome and from leaf litter and dune tussocks in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Abdomen oval, slightly flattened, covered with large scutum; dorsum brown, with delicate pattern composed of white hairs: thin median line not reaching end of abdomen, and three pairs of small patches on lateral sides (last pair, placed at spinnerets, largest) (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011). The species was described from the male, and although the female has been collected, it still needs to be described.

Figs 1–7. *Microbianor globosus*. 1, 2. Immature male from Witsand Kalahari Nature Reserve. 3. Male in alcohol, lateral view. 4. Same, dorsal view. 5–7. Male palp. Credits: 1, 2. Ruan Booysen. 3, 4, 6, 7. Charles Haddad. 5. From Haddad & Wesolowska (2011).

Microbianor simplex Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018

COMMON NAME: Witteberg Microbianor Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described in 2018 from Witteberg Nature Reserve. It is only known from the type locality (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 931 m a.s.l.). Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.34, 20.50).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dwelling species collected in woodland in the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The species is only known from the male (Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018).

Microbianor simplex Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018

Figs 1–2. *Microbianor simplex* 1. Male habitus. 2. Male alp. Credits: From Wesolowska & Haddad (2018).

GENUS *MODUNDA* Simon, 1901

The genus *Modunda* Simon, 1901 is known from three species (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: Modunda Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Modunda staintoni* (O. Pickard–Cambridge, 1872).

MORPHOLOGY: The group is characterized by the longer and more flattened form of the cephalothorax and abdomen compared to other Harmochirini. Carapace relatively short, roundish-oval in shape when viewed from above; dorsal surface flat, posterior slope abrupt; deep rich brown on sides, with black margin: caput black, encircled by band of white hairs running around the front directly beneath eyes, ending laterally behind posterior eyes; white spot in posterior half. Legs variable in length; those of second, third and fourth pairs are short, those of third pair apparently shortest; first pair are much longer than others; all tarsi end in strong claw tufts. Abdomen elongate-oval, rather flattened above, projecting over base of carapace.

LIFESTYLE: *Modunda* species are usually found in low vegetation and on tree trunks. They prefer warm, dry environments and are often cryptic in coloration to blend with their surroundings

TAXONOMY: Only one species that is widespread throughout Africa, continuing to India, is known from South Africa.

Fig. 1. *Modunda staintoni* (photographer unknown).

Modunda staintoni (O.P.–Cambridge, 1872)

COMMON NAME: Modunda Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Pantropical species described in 1872. In South Africa, it has only been recorded from KwaZulu-Natal so far (EOO=<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 47 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide global range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Southern Asia, Middle East and Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24).

LIFESTYLE: In South Africa, it is only known from a single specimen collected from bark of the fever tree bark (Haddad, 2016) and several specimens collected by beating the foliage of shrubs.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species has a wide global range with no known threats.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Recognized by the black abdomen with a crescent-shaped fringe of white setae anteriorly and the five white spots in the posterior half, which are formed by white scales.

Figs 1–10. *Modunda staintoni*. 1. Male habitus. 2–4. Female in alcohol, dorsal (2), ventral (3) and lateral (4) views. 5. Female. 6. Female, leg I. 7. Male, leg I. 8, 9. Epigyne. 10. Male palp. Credits: 1. Photographer unknown. 2–4, 6, 9. Charles Haddad. 8. From Proszynski (2017). 5, 7, 10. From Wesołowska & Tomasiewicz (2008).

GENUS *MOGRUS* Simon, 1882

The genus *Mogrus* Simon, 1882 is known from 29 species (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

COMMON NAME: White-Bearded Jumping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Mogrus fulvovittatus* Simon, 1882

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace high with very steep posterior slope. Eye field rather short. Colouration of carapace brown, dense brown hairs on whole carapace, long brown bristles near eyes. Anterior lateral eyes surrounded by fawn scales. Chelicerae long, with very dense long white hairs forming dense "beards" on their anterior surfaces. Labium and maxillae brown with pale tips, sternum brown. Abdomen broadest midway, first legs slightly darker than others. Long brown and whitish hairs on legs.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Two species recorded from South Africa.

Figs 1–3. *Mogrus* spp. Credits: 1. Charles Haddad. 2. Peter Webb. 3. Ross Hawkins.

Mogrus albogularis Simon, 1901

COMMON NAME: White-Throated Mogrus Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1901 from Kimberley in the Northern Cape and Vryburg in North West. It is known from five provinces (EOO=293 227 km²; AOO=36 km²; 271–1345 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.16, 30.23); **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ladysmith (-28.55, 29.76); Ngotsche district, Farm Vergeval (-27.35, 31.61); Zululand (-28.33, 31.08). **Limpopo:** Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47); Vhembe Biosphere, Farm Ludwig's Lust (-22.24, 29.77). **North West:** Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. It is presently protected in the Isandlwane Nature Reserve, Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009) and Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only the male is known (Simon, 1901).

Mogrus mathisi (Berland & Millot, 1941)

COMMON NAME: White-Bearded Jumping Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1941 as *Phileus mathisi* from Senegal. It has a wide distribution throughout Africa, Saudi Arabia and Yemen. In Africa, it is known from five countries, and in South Africa, from six provinces (EOO=153 289 km²; AOO=44 km²; 902–1513 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide global range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Saudi Arabia, Yemen, and in Africa from Niger, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.59, 26.43); Boshoff, Farm Boesmansrus (-28.54, 25.17). **Gauteng:** Dinokeng Private Farm (-25.40, 28.38); Pretoria/Tshwane, Hatfield (-25.74, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.41, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Spienkop Nature Reserve (-28.70, 29.49); Emnambithi/Ladysmith (-28.598, 29.759)*. **Limpopo:** Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.41, 26.75); Kruger National Park (-22.35, 31.16)*; Soutpansberg Conservancy (-23.21, 29.51); Tuinplaas (-24.90, 28.73). **North West:** Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant-dweller sampled from the Grassland and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: In South Africa, the species is protected in eight reserves.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Figs 1–9. *Mogrus mathisi*. 1. Female. 2. Male. 3. Female in alcohol. 4. Male in alcohol. 5. Male, ante-rodorsal view of carapace. 6, 7. Male palp. 8, 9. Epigyne. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Ross Hawkins. 3–6, 8. Charles Haddad. 7, 9. From Wesolowska & Van Harten (2007).

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